

BOTANY

QUANTITATIVE OCCURRENCE OF EUROPEAN MISTLETOE (*VISCUM ALBUM* L. SUBSP. *ALBUM*) IN POPLAR STANDS IN THE AREA OF NESSEBAR (SOUTHERN BLACK SEA COAST)

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Abstract

European mistletoe (*Viscum album* L. subsp. *album*) is increasingly abundant in coastal and urban habitats of Europe, but quantitative data from dune-associated plantations remain limited. In this study, artificial poplar stands within approximately 12 km² around Nessebar (Bulgaria) were surveyed. For each tree, diameter at breast height (DBH) and number of mistletoe clusters were recorded. A total of 3,047 mistletoe individuals were counted, ranging from 1 to 39 clusters per tree. The mean abundance was 2.6 clusters per tree overall and 5.2 per infested tree. *Populus × canadensis* dominated the stands (95.8% of poplars) and was the only infested species, with 50.2% of individuals carrying mistletoe. Infestation frequency and intensity increased with host size, showing moderate positive correlations with DBH (Pearson $r = 0.47$; Spearman $\rho = 0.52$). A regression model explained 22% of the variation, suggesting that other factors such as dispersal and microclimate also play a role. The population displayed an aggregated pattern, with most trees uninfested or lightly colonized, while a minority carried heavy parasite loads. These results provide a quantitative baseline for assessing mistletoe dynamics in vulnerable dune-linked plantations.

Keywords: Plants, hosts, semiparasitism, dunes, *Populus*.

Introduction

The genus *Viscum* comprises approximately 100 obligate hemiparasitic plant species distributed mainly in Africa, Asia, and Europe [13]. Among them, the European mistletoe (*Viscum album* L.) is gaining increasing importance in both natural and urbanized habitats across Europe. The species has been recorded on more than 384 host species, which accounts for its broad geographical and ecological range [14]. In Bulgaria, *V. album* is represented by three subspecies: *ssp. album*, *ssp. abietis*, and *ssp. austriacum*, the first of which parasitizes broadleaved trees and poses a serious threat to their health condition [2].

Studies in Europe focusing on the quantitative characteristics of *V. album* populations and their host trees are relatively scarce and most often address the health condition of infested trees. The study in Łódź, Poland [8] recorded 2,147 mistletoe-infested trees across 28 host taxa, with a strong preference for alien, planted species such as *Acer saccharinum*, *Populus × canadensis*, and *Robinia pseudoacacia*. Infection prevalence was higher in taller trees and in the city center, suggesting that mistletoe dispersal and survival are influenced by tree size and urban environmental conditions, particularly nitrogen input. In a survey of 956 urban trees in Kharkiv (Ukraine) by [11], mistletoe-infested trees showed a significantly worse health index (2.98 ± 0.08) compared to non-infested trees ($2.43 \pm$

0.03), with the difference being statistically significant ($\lambda = 3.14$; $P > 0.999$). A positive correlation was found between mistletoe abundance and tree age ($\rho = 0.36$), as well as between infestation severity and tree health index ($\rho = 0.23$). In a study of 200 trees in Cannock Chase (UK), a strong positive correlation was found between mistletoe density and crown defoliation, with heavily infested trees losing over 70% of foliage. *Tilia cordata* proved significantly more vulnerable than *Acer pseudoplatanus*, while low soil moisture and high light availability further exacerbated mistletoe-induced damage [15].

The coastal dune complexes of the Bulgarian Black Sea coast represent vulnerable and dynamic systems, including types such as embryo dunes, mobile dunes, and fixed dunes [6], often covered with *Populus*, *Salix*, *Robinia*, and other host tree species. This structural and biotic base makes dunes both potentially vulnerable and relevant for the study of *V. album ssp. album*. Several studies in Bulgaria identify poplars as the main vector for the spread of European mistletoe, especially along the Black Sea coast, where in some areas its populations reach significant sizes [1, 2, 4, 5].

The aim of the present study is to analyze the quantitative parameters of the population, distribution, and impact of European mistletoe (*V. album* L. *ssp. album*) in poplar stands in the region of Nessebar.

Materials and methods

Object of study

The study focuses on artificial poplar plantations in the area of the Nessebar dune complexes. The survey area covers approximately 12 km² and includes parts of compartments 561, 562, and 563 as defined in the current Forest Management Plan (2019–2028) for the State

Hunting Ground Nessebar, Regional Forest Directorate–Burgas, where poplar (*Populus* sp.) and black locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia* L.) plantations predominate (Fig. 1). The prevailing age of the poplars in these stands is 20–40 years, with occasional older individuals present.

Fig. 1. Map of distribution of the prevailing artificial plantations of poplars (green marks) in the study area (based on data from the current Forest Management Plan (2019–2028) of the State Hunting Ground Nessebar, Regional Forest Directorate Burgas)

The climate of the area is strongly influenced by the Black Sea and the Mediterranean, and is characterized by high humidity, relatively high mean air temperatures, and a greater number of sunny days. The soils are Arenosols with their typical loamy-sand to sand texture, high contents of quartz sand and carbonates, and a slightly alkaline to alkaline reaction [2]

Methodological approach

A census of all individuals of the genus *Populus* was conducted within the study area, and the number and species of trees infested with European mistletoe (*V. album* ssp. *album*) were determined. In this study, the name Canadian poplar (*Populus × canadensis* Moench) is treated as a synonym of Euro-American poplar (*Populus × euramericana* Guinier) following [10]. Information on the taxonomy and biological characteristics of Euro-American poplar cultivars follows [3]. For each tree, the following variables were recorded:

1. **Tree diameter at breast height (DBH, cm)** – measured at 1.3 m above ground with a diameter tape.
2. **Number of mistletoe individuals (clusters) per tree** – counted visually for the entire crown of each tree.

Based on these measurements, several population characteristics were derived:

- **Population size and prevalence** – total number of mistletoe clusters recorded in the sample, absolute number of infected vs. non-infected trees, and the proportion (%) of infected individuals.

- **Population density** – mean number of mistletoe clusters per tree (all trees) and mean number per infected tree only.

- **Distribution of infestation** – frequency distribution of mistletoe clusters per tree (histogram) to illustrate the spread of infestation intensities across the population.

- **Structural (size-class analysis)** – grouping of host trees into diameter classes of 10 cm intervals (e.g., 0–10, 10–20, 20–30 cm, etc.). For each class, the number of trees, number of infected trees, percentage of infection, and mean mistletoe load were calculated. This approach allows assessment of how infestation varies with host size. Such grouping methods are commonly used in ecology to study population structure and dynamics [9].

- **Correlation and regression analysis** – relationships between tree diameter and mistletoe abundance were tested using:

- Pearson's correlation coefficient (linear association).
- Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (monotonic association).
- Simple linear regression, modelling the number of mistletoe clusters per tree as a function of tree diameter. The coefficient of determination (R^2) was used to evaluate the explanatory power of diameter.

- **Population structure** – boxplots and class-based comparisons were used to assess the variation in infestation intensity among trees of different diameter

classes, highlighting the heterogeneity within the host population.

For the statistical processing of the data, descriptive statistics were applied – means, medians, modes, minimum and maximum values, as well as relative proportions of infected trees. Such indicators are standard in studies of biological and ecological populations [16]. To evaluate the relationship between tree diameter (DBH) and the number of mistletoe (*Viscum album*) clusters, Pearson's correlation coefficient (for linear association) and Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (for monotonic association) were calculated. These methods are widely applied in ecological data analysis when assessing the strength and direction of relationships between quantitative or ordinal variables [12]. For a more detailed modelling of the relationship, a simple linear regression was fitted, considering the number of mistletoe clusters per tree as the dependent variable and tree diameter as the independent variable. The explanatory power of diameter on mistletoe abundance was evaluated using the coefficient of determination (R^2), which is a standard approach in biostatistics [7]. For structural analysis, trees were grouped into diameter classes (10 cm intervals). For each class, the infection frequency (percentage of infected trees), mean number of mistletoe clusters per infected tree, and the total number of clusters were calculated. This methodology provides a comprehensive characterisation of

mistletoe population parameters, combining descriptive statistics with structural and relational analyses. It allows for both quantification of infestation levels and evaluation of the factors influencing the spread of *Viscum album*.

Results

The population of European mistletoe parasitizing poplars in the studied area consists of **3,047 individuals**. The number of mistletoe clusters per tree ranges from **1 to 39**. The mean abundance across all host trees is **2.6 clusters per tree**, which, given the bio-ecological characteristics of the species, may be considered as the population density. When only infested trees are considered, the mean number rises to **5.2 clusters per tree**. The median number of clusters per tree is **10**, while the mode (the most frequent value) is **0**. The spatial extent of the mistletoe population coincides with the study area of **12 km²**.

The diameter of host trees ranged from **10 to 76 cm**, with a mean of **24.1 cm** and a median of **21 cm**. The proportion of trees infested with mistletoe was as follows: **49.8% uninfested, 34.0% with 1–5 clusters, and 6.6% with more than 10 clusters**. Among all representatives of the genus *Populus* in the area, **95.8% belong to *Populus × canadensis* Moench** (cultivars '*Regenerata*' and '*Bachelieri*') (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Canadian poplar plantations in sample plots with medium to high levels of European mistletoe infestation (photo P. Glogov)

The distribution of the remaining *Populus* species is as follows: 3.9% white poplar (*Populus alba* L.); 0.3% Lombardy poplar *Populus pyramidalis* Rozier (syn. *Populus nigra* f. *italica*, *Populus nigra* subsp. *pyramidalis* Čelak). From the distribution of species by

the percentage of individuals infested with mistletoe (Table 1), it is evident that infestation was recorded only in Canadian poplar.

Table 1.

Quantitative distribution of *Viscum album* individuals among host tree species

Tree species	Total number of trees	Percentage of trees infested by mistletoe (%)	Total number of mistletoe individuals (clusters)
<i>Populus × canadensis</i>	1158	50,2	3047
<i>Populus alba</i>	47	0	0
<i>Populus pyramidalis</i>	4	0	0

Half of the trees in the stands were infected with mistletoe, with the number of clusters varying considerably (from 1 to 39) (Table 2). With increasing diameter, both the proportion of infested trees and the mean number of mistletoes increased – for example, in the 10–20 cm class about 38% were infested, whereas in

the 40–50 cm class the proportion reached 77%. This is a characteristic feature of *Viscum album* populations: infection accumulates with the age and size of trees. Despite this clear trend, the regression model indicates that additional factors (spatial distribution, bird dispersers, microclimate) also influence the variation.

Table 2.

Quantitative distribution of mistletoe clusters in relation to host tree diameter classes

Diameter class	Number of host trees	Number of infested host trees	Share (%) of infested host trees	Mean number of clusters per all host trees	Mean number of clusters per infested host trees	Total number of clusters
0–10 cm	1	1	100.0	2.0	2.0	2
10–20 cm	426	161	37.8	0.86	2.27	366
20–30 cm	453	233	51.4	2.59	5.04	1174
30–40 cm	207	132	63.8	4.67	7.32	966
40–50 cm	64	49	76.6	7.36	9.61	471
50–60 cm	7	6	85.7	9.71	11.33	68
60–70 cm	1	0	0.0	0.0	–	0

The histogram of mistletoe abundance per tree reveals (Fig 3) that the largest proportion of host trees carry between 0 and 5 mistletoe clusters. With increasing infestation levels, the frequency of trees gradually declines, indicating that higher numbers of clusters per tree are progressively less common. Nevertheless, a few extreme cases were recorded, with individual trees hosting more than 30 clusters, demonstrating that heavy

infestation, although rare, does occur. Overall, the population of *Viscum album* displays a mosaic distribution: the majority of trees are either uninfested or only lightly infested, whereas a relatively small proportion is heavily colonized. This pattern is typical for parasitic plants, where spread and establishment are largely governed by stochastic processes such as seed dispersal by birds.

Fig. 3. Histogram showing the distribution of mistletoe clusters across host trees

The relationship between tree diameter and mistletoe abundance (Fig 4) shows a clear positive trend: as diameter increases, the number of mistletoe clusters also tends to rise. Although the data points are scattered, the overall upward slope of the regression line is evident. Larger trees may host several dozen clusters, while smaller individuals rarely carry more than a few. This pattern highlights tree size as a key factor influ-

encing infestation intensity. Both the likelihood of mistletoe presence and the number of clusters increase with tree age and size. Nevertheless, the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.22$) indicates that tree diameter alone explains only part of the variation, suggesting that additional factors such as stand location, bird disperser activity, and microclimatic conditions also play important roles.

Fig. 4. Relationship between host tree diameter and the quantitative occurrence of *Viscum album*

The distribution of mistletoe abundance across diameter classes (Fig. 5) demonstrates a clear size-related pattern. In each successive class, both the median number of clusters and the degree of variation increase with tree diameter. Small trees (diameter 10–20 cm) show consistently low and relatively uniform infestation levels, whereas in the 40–50 cm class and above, the variability becomes much greater. Among the larger diam-

eter classes, extreme values (“outliers”) are also present, with some individual trees carrying disproportionately high numbers of clusters.

These findings suggest that mistletoe accumulation over time results in increasing variability within the population. Older trees include both moderately and heavily infested individuals, indicating differences in susceptibility among hosts, as well as the likely influence of local site conditions and spatial factors.

Fig. 5. Boxplot showing the distribution of mistletoe clusters by host tree diameter classes

The statistical analysis of the relationship between tree diameter and mistletoe infestation was carried out using three complementary approaches. **Pearson’s correlation coefficient ($r = 0.47$)** indicates the strength of a linear relationship between tree diameter at breast height (DBH) and the number of mistletoe clusters. The obtained value ($r = 0.47$) reflects a moderately positive association, meaning that larger trees tend to host more mistletoe. However, since the coefficient is not close to 1, the relationship is far from perfect and additional factors clearly contribute to the variation. **Spearman’s**

rank correlation ($\rho = 0.52$) captures monotonic rather than strictly linear relationships. The slightly higher value compared to Pearson’s coefficient suggests that the general tendency—larger trees carrying more mistletoe—is more robust when examined in terms of ranked values. In practice, smaller trees usually bear few or no clusters, whereas larger trees more frequently support higher numbers of mistletoe. A simple linear regression quantified the relationship between DBH (independent variable) and the number of mistletoe clusters (dependent variable). The model ($y = 0.13$,

DBH – 0.49) indicates that each additional centimeter of tree diameter is associated with an average increase of 0.13 clusters. While this increment appears small, it scales considerably: for example, a tree 70 cm larger in diameter than another is expected to carry approximately nine more clusters.

Discussion

The present study provides a comprehensive quantitative characterization of *Viscum album* subsp. *album* populations in coastal poplar stands of the Nessebar region. The total number of recorded mistletoe individuals exceeded 3,000, distributed across more than half of the surveyed trees. Such a high proportion of infestation demonstrates the strong capacity of mistletoe to establish and spread in artificially created stands dominated by *Populus × canadensis*. The mean population density of 2.6 clusters per tree (5.2 clusters per infested tree) indicates that mistletoe is not evenly distributed, but rather occurs in concentrated foci of infestation, consistent with the mosaic patterns typically reported for hemiparasitic plants.

The frequency analysis confirmed that the majority of trees were either uninfested or carried only a few clusters, while a smaller fraction of the population sustained high levels of infestation, with extreme cases exceeding 30 clusters per tree. This strongly skewed distribution reflects the role of stochastic factors such as seed deposition by birds, combined with local site conditions, in shaping population structure.

The increased infestation rate of *Populus × canadensis* by European mistletoe confirms the findings of [2], who reported that non-native poplar species in the study region are more frequently attacked by this hemiparasite. This can be attributed both to the widespread cultivation of hybrid poplars and to the removal of many mature individuals of *Populus alba* at the end of the 20th and the beginning of the 21st century, which had previously served as an important vector for mistletoe spread among native poplars in the area. A favorable factor for the development of poplar plantations is the slightly alkaline soil reaction combined with the light mechanical composition of the soils. At the same time, increased carbonate content in certain areas, as well as soil compaction leading to reduced aeration, may contribute to the deterioration of the overall condition of the stands or of individual trees. The absence of mistletoe on Lombardy poplar is consistent with the generally rare infestations of this species reported elsewhere [8]. The established direct relationship between tree diameter (age), the number of mistletoe individuals of host trees has also been observed in other tree species [15]. No significant difference in the level of infestation (number of mistletoe individuals) was found between the two *Populus × canadensis* cultivars, ‘Regenerata’ and ‘Bachelieri’, during the study.

Conclusions

The quantitative assessment revealed that mistletoe is a widespread and abundant parasite in the poplar stands of Nessebar, with more than 50% of trees infested and a total population exceeding 3,000 individuals within 12 km². Infestation is highly aggregated: most trees remain uninfested or lightly colonized, while a smaller fraction hosts heavy parasite loads. Such a

distribution is characteristic of hemiparasitic plants and reflects the combined influence of bird-mediated dispersal and site-specific conditions.

The almost exclusive dependence on *Populus × canadensis* as a host highlights both the ecological vulnerability of plantations dominated by this hybrid and the role of species composition in shaping parasite populations.

At this stage, no difference in the degree of mistletoe infestation has been established between the two cultivars ‘Regenerata’ and ‘Bachelieri’. A positive relationship between stem diameter and the number of *V. album* individuals was confirmed. Further research is needed to assess the potential significance of variations in soil pH, carbonate content, and soil texture, and their relationship with the quantitative occurrence of mistletoe in the plantations.

Overall, the study demonstrates that quantitative parameters—population size, density, and frequency distribution—are essential for understanding the population ecology of *V. album* and for developing effective monitoring and management approaches in vulnerable dune habitats.

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